

MACHINE LEARNING-BASED INVESTIGATIONS ON NONLINEAR VIBRATIONS OF CFRP COMPOSITE

Jia-ao Hou, School of Transportation Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing 100191, China, jiaao@buaa.edu.cn

Chao Wu *, School of Transportation Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing 100191, China, wuchao@buaa.edu.cn

Yangping Yao, School of Transportation Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing 100191, China, ypyao@buaa.edu.cn

Renyan Qin, School of Environmental and Civil Engineering, Dongguan University of Technology, Dongguan 523000, China, qinry@dgut.edu.cn

Denvid Lau, Department of Architecture and Civil Engineering, City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, China, denvid.lau@cityu.edu.hk

Lik-ho Tam *, School of Transportation Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing 100191, China, leo_tam@buaa.edu.cn

* Corresponding authors: E-mail: leo_tam@buaa.edu.cn (Lik-ho Tam); wuchao@buaa.edu.cn (Chao Wu).

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite has been increasingly used in constructions, which is subjected to external loads that cause severe nonlinear vibrations and final structural failure. In this work, a machine learning approach is adopted to investigate nonlinear vibrations of CFRP composite. A dataset about nonlinear frequency ratios of CFRP composite under different load levels, sizes, and boundary conditions is established, which is used to train prediction model. Using developed model, attribute importance of nonlinear vibration and nonlinear frequency ratios under various conditions are investigated. The finding of this work contributes to predicting long-term vibration properties of CFRP composite.

KEYWORDS: CFPR composite; Nonlinear vibration; Compression load; Machine learning; Prediction model

INTRODUCTION

Due to exceptional properties and strong corrosion resistance, CFRP composite has been increasingly used in civil engineering, such as structural components for building and bridge constructions, as shown in **Figure 1a** (Q. Chen & Liu, 2011; Z. Wang et al., 2017). During intended service life, the CFRP application is subjected to various external excitations, such as compression loads from traffic movements and wind or flowing water pressure, which lead to large structural deformation, as shown in **Figure 1b** (Wu et al., 2023; Xu, Thwe, Shearwood, & Liao, 2002). When the ratio of the deflection caused by structural deformation to the thickness of CFRP composite is larger than 0.4, it significantly changes the loading condition of system and further leads to nonlinear vibration of CFRP composite (Rafiee, Liu, He, & Kitipornchai, 2014). Long-term severe vibrations with large amplitudes result in surface cracks, which eventually lead to structural failure, as shown in **Figure 1c**. In real applications, CFRP composite possesses various sizes and boundary conditions. The combination of these factors has a synergistic effect on the nonlinear vibration behavior of CFRP composite plate, which makes the prediction of nonlinear frequency a challenging task in the field. In order to avoid the structural failure of CFRP composite caused by nonlinear vibrations, it is crucial to understand vibration responses of CFRP composite under different compression load levels, sizes, and boundary conditions, during intended service life.

Figure 1 Carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite is subjected to nonlinear vibration.

Experimental and numerical investigations have been conducted to explore vibration properties of CFRP composite under different conditions, such as load levels and length-to-width ratios (Jamal-Omidi & ShayanMehr, 2017; Shen, 2015). Specifically, in a recent experimental study on nonlinear vibration of CFRP composite plate, it is reported that with increasing external axial compression load levels from 10 to 80 kN, nonlinear frequency of CFRP composite plate increased by 66.7%, and with length-to-width ratio of CFRP plate increased from 1.00 to 1.50, nonlinear frequency ratio increased by 18.4%, which indicates that nonlinear vibration becomes more severe with increasing load levels (Jamal-Omidi & ShayanMehr, 2017). Notably, nonlinear frequency ratio is the ratio of nonlinear frequency to linear frequency, where nonlinear frequency is the frequency that varies with vibration amplitude under loading on the system and linear frequency does not vary with vibration amplitude or external loads. Similar result has been reported in a numerical study, where nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate increased by 90% with increasing compression load level from 0 to 265 MPa (Shen, 2015). From previous investigations, it is learned that nonlinear vibrations of CFRP composite became more severe with increasing load levels, while only several sizes of CFRP composite are considered. Therefore, it remains unclear about the vibration behaviors of CFRP composite under various load levels, sizes, and boundary conditions, which hinders the systematic investigations on vibration properties of composite in real applications.

Machine learning approach simulates the complex cognitive laws of human brain and captures the rules between large amounts of data, which has been proven to be an accurate and efficient approach for solving nonlinear regression problems, and for predicting vibration behaviors of composite materials (Atilla, Sencan, Goren Kiral, & Kiral, 2020; V. Kallannavar et al., 2021; X. Q. Wang, Chen, Chow, & Lau, 2023). Specifically, vibration response of CFRP composite plate with circular holes in the plate center was investigated using Levenberg–Marquardt backpropagation algorithm, which was trained using natural frequency of plate with different circular holes obtained from finite element (FE) simulation (Atilla et al., 2020). It is reported that natural frequency of CFRP composite with hole was predicted as 45.6 Hz, which is close to the FE simulation result of 44.4 Hz, and the overall accuracy of the prediction was 97% for the CFRP composite plate with different holes. In another machine learning investigation, a prediction model of vibration property of CFRP composite was trained using FE simulation results, including sizes and boundary conditions of composite plate (V. Kallannavar et al., 2021). It is shown that the predicted accuracy of the model was 92% for the non-dimensional nature frequencies of CFRP composite with different sizes and boundary conditions. From previous machine learning investigations, it is learned that the values of nonlinear frequency of CFRP composite under effect of external load still remain unclear, which are essential to analyse durability of CFRP composite in real applications.

In this work, nonlinear vibrations of CFRP composite plate with different sizes and boundary conditions under various compression load levels are investigated using a developed machine learning approach. Specifically, using experimental and numerical results as inputs, a dataset of vibration responses of CFRP composite plate under different compression load levels, sizes, and boundary conditions is established. Due to the different amount of data in each condition, in order to achieve a comprehensive training, 80% of the data in each condition is selected as training set to train the prediction model of

nonlinear vibration, which is the commonly used percentage in machine learning investigation, and the remaining 20% are used as testing set. With the developed prediction model, nonlinear frequency ratios of CFRP composite plate under different loading levels are predicted, which are compared with the values in testing set to validate the prediction model. Afterwards, nonlinear frequency ratios of CFRP composite plates are predicted under a series of compression loading levels, sizes, and boundary conditions using the validated prediction model. The developed machine learning model contributes to the investigation of nonlinear vibrations of CFRP composite plate, which is essential for predicting durability of CFRP composite during intended service life.

INVESTIGATION DETAILS

The nonlinear frequency ratios of CFRP composite collected from existing literatures are used to establish dataset. The dataset is applied to train the prediction model, which is developed using extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) algorithm. Afterwards, the prediction model is employed to predict nonlinear frequency ratios of CFRP composite under various conditions. The details are given as follows.

Dataset determination

In order to develop an accurate prediction model of nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate, it is essential to establish a comprehensive dataset. In this work, a dataset about nonlinear vibrations of CFRP composite is developed based on an extensive literature review, which involves a total of 226 data points. Specifically, 80% (181 data points) of the data is selected as training set to train the prediction model, and the remaining 20% (45 data points) are used as testing set (Bouazza & Zenkour, 2020; C.-S. Chen, Cheng, Chien, & Doong, 2002; Fallah & Delzendeh, 2018; Harras, Benamar, & White, 2002; Vinayak Kallannavar, Kumaran, & Kattimani, 2020; Khalili, Malekzadeh, & Mittal, 2005; Mao, Lai, Zhang, & Liu, 2021; Tang & Dai, 2021; Tang, Dai, & Liao, 2020; Z.-X. Wang & Shen, 2011; Zhang, Cui, & Liew, 2015). The dataset encompasses a wide range of load levels, length-to-width ratios a/b , width-to-thickness ratios b/h , and boundary conditions of CFRP composite plate, as shown in **Table 1**. Load level is the value of compression load applied to CFRP composite plate, the meanings of length a , width b , and thickness h of CFRP composite plate are shown clearly in **Figure 2** respectively, and different boundary conditions are also displayed in **Figure 2**.

Table 1 Attributes and data ranges of collected dataset

Variable	Unit	Data range	Type
Load level	MPa	[0.00, 800.00]	Input
Length-to-width ratio (a/b)	%	[1.00, 1.80]	Input
Width-to-thickness ratio (b/h)	%	[10.00, 100.00]	Input
Boundary condition	%	Four edges simply supported (SSSS); a pair of opposite edges clamped and left edges simply supported (CSCS); four edges clamped supported (CCCC)	Input
Nonlinear frequency ratio	/	[1.00, 4.84]	Output

Figure 2 The parameters of CFRP composite plate, including size and boundary condition.

Specifically, the range of load level is selected to be from 0.00 to 800.00 MPa, which is the maximum load level reported in the literature. For length-to-width ratio a/b and width-to-thickness ratio b/h , it is shown that ranges are from 1.00 to 1.80 and from 10.00 to 100.00 respectively, which are commonly used in real applications. As for boundary condition, it is found that three conditions are included in dataset, including four edges simply supported (SSSS), a pair of opposite edges clamped and left edges simply supported (CSCS), and four edges clamped supported (CCCC), as they are widely used in CFRP applications. As it is necessary to parameterize all the information in dataset for constructing the prediction model, the boundary conditions SSSS, CSCS, and CCCC are parameterized as value 1, 2, and 3, respectively. Afterwards, all the information of data is parameterized into a structured vector, which is used in prediction model, as described subsequently. It is noted that, physical properties of CFRP composite also make influences on nonlinear frequency ratios. The dataset used in this paper is from CFRP composite plates that all possess similar physical properties, including the fiber volume (1%) and fiber distribution (uniform distribution), Young's modulus (7.59-8.28 GPa) and Poisson's ratio (0.30-0.32) (Azzara, Carrera, & Pagani, 2022; Vinayak Kallannavar et al., 2020; Shen, 2015). Therefore, it is believed that the developed prediction model is able to predict the nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate with similar physical properties.

Prediction model development

Afterwards, the collected dataset is trained using XGBoost algorithm to develop the prediction model. The mathematical fundamentals of XGBoost algorithm used in this work is introduced briefly as follows. It is considered that the dataset for XGBoost algorithm is described as Eq. 1,

$$D \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_i, y_i)\} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where x_i is the input variable with several attributes and y_i is the real value for validation purpose. The XGBoost algorithm is mathematically expressed using Eq. 2,

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x_i) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where \hat{y}_i is the predicted value respecting input x_i , T denotes the total number of regression trees, and f_t represents the predicted value of each independent regression tree. After the prediction result is obtained, the objective function L_o is required to evaluate the quality of prediction results on training set, as shown in Eq. 3,

$$L_o = \sum_i^n l(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{k=1}^K \Omega(f_k) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where l is loss function measuring the distance between predicted value \hat{y}_i and real value y_i , as shown in Eq. 4, and Ω is the regularization item that penalizes the complexity of tree structure to make XGBoost a simple tree structure while avoiding overfitting. The specific form of Ω for one regression tree is described using Eq. 5,

$$l(y_i, \hat{y}_i) = (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\Omega(f_k) = \gamma H + \frac{1}{2} \alpha \sum_{k=1}^H |w_k| + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \sum_{k=1}^H w_k^2 \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where H is total number of leaf nodes of a regression tree, w_k is predicted value of the k th leaf node, and γ , α , and λ are hyperparameters of the algorithm. With increasing γ , α , and λ , the penalty for structural complexity of regression tree increases, indicating that more complex tree leads to higher penalty. In order to minimize the objective function and achieve the best prediction result, training of prediction model is needed, which is conducted through a step-by-step manner. In each step, a new regression tree is generated based on existing regression trees, and the objective function is further reduced. The objective function of the m th step $L_o^{(m)}$ is calculated based on the previous step $L_o^{(m-1)}$, as shown in Eq. 6,

$$\begin{aligned}
L_o^{(m)} &= \sum_i^n l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(m)}) + \sum_{i=1}^m \Omega(f_i) \\
&= \sum_i^n l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(m-1)} + f_m(x_i)) + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \Omega(f_i) + \Omega(f_m)
\end{aligned} \tag{Eq. 6}$$

where the existing $(m-1)$ regression trees are known and considered as a constant number x in the m th step. Afterwards, $L_o^{(m)}$ is described as Eq. 7,

$$L_o^{(m)} = \sum_i^n l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(m-1)} + f_m(x_i)) + \Omega(f_m) + x \tag{Eq. 7}$$

Furthermore, by applying the second-order Taylor expansion to Eq. 7, the objection function is transformed into Eqs. 8-10

$$L_o^{(m)} = \sum_i^n \left[l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(m-1)} + g_i f_m(x_i) + \frac{1}{2} h_i f_m^2(x_i)) \right] + \Omega(f_m) + x \tag{Eq. 8}$$

$$g_i = \frac{\partial l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(m-1)})}{\partial \hat{y}_i^{(m-1)}} \tag{Eq. 9}$$

$$h_i = \frac{\partial^2 l(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(m-1)})}{\partial (\hat{y}_i^{(m-1)})^2} \tag{Eq. 10}$$

Afterwards, substituting Eqs. 4 and 5 into Eq. 8, the objective function is described as Eq. 11,

$$\begin{aligned}
L_o^{(m)} &= \sum_i^n \left[g_i f_m(x_i) + \frac{1}{2} h_i f_m^2(x_i) \right] + \Omega(f_m) + x \\
&= \sum_i^n \left[G_j \omega_j + \frac{1}{2} (H_j + \lambda) \omega_j^2 \right] + \gamma T + x
\end{aligned} \tag{Eq. 11}$$

where $G_j = \sum_i g_i$ and $H_j = \sum_i h_i$. The minimum value of objective function $L_o^{(m)}$ is determined by describing ω_j as Eq. 12, and the minimum value of objective function L_G is described as Eq. 13,

$$\omega_j = -\frac{G_j}{H_j + \lambda} \tag{Eq. 12}$$

$$L_G = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{G_L^2}{H_L + \lambda} + \frac{G_R^2}{H_R + \lambda} - \frac{(G_L + G_R)^2}{H_L + H_R + \lambda} \right) - \gamma \tag{Eq. 13}$$

Afterwards, the hyperparameters of prediction model are determined to optimize prediction results, including tree-number, learning-rate, max-depth, min-child-weight, subsample, colsample-by tree, and several regularization factors, as shown in **Table 2** (T. Chen & Guestrin, 2016). Tree-number is the number of regression trees in prediction model, learning-rate defines the step size of each training round, max-depth represents the number of branches from root node to leaf node of a regression tree, min-child-weight defines the complexity of a regression tree, subsample indicates the ratio of training set to the total dataset of a regression tree, colsample-by tree represents the ratio of training attributes to total attributes of a regression tree, and γ , α , and λ are regularization factors of the objective function in Eq. 5, which are used to prevent the model from overfitting. In order to obtain the optimal combination of hyperparameters, GridsearchCV method is adopted to find the optional parameter, which is an automated parameter tuning method that essentially employs an exhaustive search method (Liu, Liu, & Feng, 2022). The control hyperparameters used in this work are presented in **Table 2**. With all hyperparameters determined, the prediction model is finalized, and the prediction model is successfully obtained.

Table 2 Hyperparameters of XGBoost algorithm

Hyperparameters	Value
Tree-number	500
Learning-rate	0.1
Max-depth	8
Min-child-weight	4
Subsample	0.8
Colsample-by tree	0.8
Regularization factors	$\gamma = 0$
	$\alpha = 0$
	$\lambda = 1$

After the hyperparameters are determined, the prediction model is developed. Specifically, the structure of prediction model developed in this work is shown in **Figure 3**, including numerous root nodes, internal nodes, branches, and leaf nodes. During the operation of prediction model, the parameters in the established dataset are inputted into the model and delivered to all the root nodes of all trees for initial decision-making. Afterwards, the internal nodes make the decisions through the branches that contain decision conditions, and the leaf nodes represent the prediction results of each single tree. The prediction result is eventually derived by aggregating the results from all the leaf nodes.

Figure 3 Structure and operation process of prediction model: the data is inputted into the root node for initial decision, internal nodes subsequently make further decisions through branches that contain decision conditions, and ultimately prediction is derived by aggregating results from all leaf nodes.

In order to understand the effect of various influential factors, XGBoost algorithm is adopted to analyze the attribute importance of each influential factor, which is known to have a good interpretability in terms of the output results (Bentéjac, Csörgő, & Martínez-Muñoz, 2021; Liu et al., 2022). All attributes related to the prediction results are quantitatively described using an F-score, which indicates the contribution of an attribute in XGBoost algorithm. Specifically, during decision-making process, the F-score of an attribute is determined by calculating its optimization to each tree objective function in the model, and the F-score of a particular attribute increases when this attribute is increasingly used in the prediction process. Afterwards, in order to evaluate performance of the prediction model, four statistical criteria are employed to evaluate the performance of the proposed model, including R^2 , RMSE, MAE, and MAPE, as they are widely used to evaluate the performance of machine learning model. Specifically, R^2 is used as the primary evaluation criterion to assess accuracy of prediction models, which measures the correlation between real value and predicted value, and a larger R^2 indicates a better performance of the model (Bentéjac et al., 2021). Meanwhile, RMSE, MAE and MAPE, measure the distance between real value and predicted value, and smaller values indicate better model performance. The mathematical expressions of these parameters are shown in Eqs. 14-17,

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_i (\hat{y}_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_i (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_i |\hat{y}_i - y_i|}{\sum_i |\hat{y}_i - \bar{y}|} \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

$$MAPE = \sum_i \left| \frac{\hat{y}_i - y_i}{y_i} \right| \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

where \bar{y} is the average of real values.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results measured from the developed machine learning prediction model are presented here, including nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate under various load levels, length-to-width ratios, width-to-thickness ratios, and boundary conditions. Afterwards, the importance of above attribute for CFRP composite nonlinear vibration is analyzed. Furthermore, prediction results of vibration behaviors of CFRP composite under different conditions are presented.

Model validation

In order to quantify the performance and accuracy of prediction model, prediction results are evaluated using four evaluation criteria, including R^2 , RMSE, MAE and MAPE (T. Chen & Guestrin, 2016). The evaluation results are calculated and presented in **Table 3**. It is shown that R^2 of training set and testing set of the prediction model are both greater than 0.95, which is higher compared with previous machine learning investigations using XGBoost algorithm, where R^2 of testing set were measured as 0.93 and 0.92 respectively (Feng, Wang, Mangalathu, & Taciroglu, 2021; Liu et al., 2022). The larger R^2 indicating a better correlation between XGBoost predictions and results from experimental and numerical investigations. Apart from R^2 , RMSE, MAE and MAPE in this work are less than 0.06, which correspond to the measurements less than 0.07 in previous investigations, demonstrating the excellent accuracy of the model developed in this work (Feng et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022).

Table 3 Evaluation results of prediction model

Evaluation parameter	Training set	Testing set
R^2	0.99	0.96
RMSE	0.03	0.06
MAE	0.02	0.06
MAPE	0.01	0.04

With the developed prediction model, the nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate with different conditions are obtained. The predicted nonlinear frequency ratio is plotted against the experimental and numerical results in dataset, as shown in **Figure 4**. It is observed that in the training set, the scatters nearly coincide with the ideal $y=x$ line, which indicates that the predicted nonlinear frequency ratios are very close to those obtained from experimental and numerical investigations, as shown in **Figure 4a**. For the testing set, it is observed that the data scatters are generally distributed around the $y=x$ line, while a few scatters with nonlinear frequency ratio between 1.2 and 2.1 are a bit far from the line (see **Figure 4b**). Notably, for the black and red scatters with nonlinear frequency ratio between 1.2 and 2.1 under condition of $a/b=1.0$, the results of the nonlinear frequency ratio from literatures exist 10-15% difference, while for other conditions, the difference between the nonlinear frequency ratio is small. Therefore, prediction results under these conditions (the black and red scatters) show a worse correlation compared with other conditions, especially the red scatters, which do not perform well in the training set as well. Furthermore, as the training set is directly used during

prediction process, the results outputted based on training set shows a better correlation than those outputted based on testing set, which has been reported in previous machine learning investigations (Feng et al., 2021; Wakjira, Ebead, & Alam, 2022).

Figure 4 Comparison of predicted values of CFRP composite plate.

Model interpretations

After validating the developed prediction model, the attribute importance of nonlinear frequency ratio is investigated. The F-scores of all attributes being investigated are calculated and presented in **Figure 5**, where the values are normalized. It is shown that load level possesses the F-score value of 0.532, which indicates that load level is the most influential factor of CFRP composite nonlinear vibration (Bentéjac et al., 2021; Feng et al., 2021). With the increasing load level, the deformation of composite plate significantly increases, which leads to considerable changes in dynamic stiffness and remarkable increase of nonlinear frequency while linear frequency remains the same. Finally, it leads to an increment in nonlinear frequency ratio, which causes increasing risk of structural damage (Dash & Singh, 2012; Wu et al., 2023). Apart from load level, the F-scores of length-to-width ratio a/b and width-to-thickness ratio b/h are calculated as 0.215 and 0.152, respectively. These two factors directly impact the static stiffness and mass of CFRP composite plate, which further affects nonlinear frequency ratio (Azzara et al., 2022). Furthermore, it is measured that the F-score of boundary condition is 0.101, as boundary restrictions only affect static stiffness of CFRP composite plate, which has limited effect on nonlinear vibration (Rafiee et al., 2014). From the attribute importance analysis, it is learned that the load level and the length-to-width ratio a/b are the most important external and internal factors for determining the nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate.

Figure 5 Attribute importance analysis of prediction model: the load level is the most important factor in nonlinear vibration of CFRP composite, and the a/b ratio is the most important internal factor.

Prediction results

After validating the prediction model, it is utilized to predict nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate with various load levels, length-to-width ratios a/b , width-to-thickness ratios b/h , and boundary conditions. The experimentally determined nonlinear frequency ratio and the corresponding prediction model results are presented in **Figure 6a** (Shen, 2015). It is noted that experimental results presentend here are not used during the training process reported above. It is shown that the prediction model could provide accurate predictions of nonlinear frequency ratio, with differences between experimental results and model predictions within 4%. Afterwards, using the prediction model, the value of nonlinear frequency ratio under extended load level is predicted, and the largest load level of 800 MPa is the highest load level in existing literature, which is the extreme case compared with common load level (100-400 MPa) of CFRP composite plate exposed during service life. It is observed that with increasing load level, nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate continuously increases, which indicates the more severe nonlinear vibration.

Figure 6 Predicted results of developed model: nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate.

After investigating the cases of different load levels, nonlinear vibration behaviors of CFRP composite plate with various plate sizes and boundary conditions are further investigated. With increasing length-to-width ratio a/b , it is shown that nonlinear frequency ratio increases, as shown in **Figure 6b**, which indicates that nonlinear vibration is more severe. Under different load level cases, nonlinear frequency ratio shows similar increasing trend with increasing length-to-width ratio a/b . Afterwards, the effect of

width-to-thickness ratio b/h on nonlinear vibration is investigated, as shown in **Figure 6c**. It is observed that with increasing width-to-thickness ratio b/h , nonlinear frequency ratio increases, which indicates that nonlinear vibration behavior of thin plate is worse than that of thick plate under the same load level (Z.-X. Wang & Shen, 2011). Similarly, with increasing load level, nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite increases, which indicates that increasing load level leads to more severe nonlinear vibration that increases the risk of structural damage. Furthermore, nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate with different boundary conditions is predicted, as shown in **Figure 6d**. It is observed that with increasing boundary constraint, nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate decreases, which indicates the less severe nonlinear vibration and the decreasing risk of structural damage (Khalili et al., 2005). With the continuously increasing length-to-width ratio a/b and width-to-thickness ratio b/h , and decreasing boundary constraint, the stiffness of CFRP composite plate decreases and mass increases, which leads to more severe nonlinear vibration and an increasing risk of structural damage of CFRP composite.

According to the prediction results, when length-to-width ratio a/b and width-to-thickness ratio b/h of CFRP composite in real applications are 1.0 and 10.0 respectively, and boundary condition is clamped supported, the CFRP composite exhibits less severe nonlinear vibration behaviors, which indicates a decreasing risk of structural damage and better durability. In order to characterize modes of vibration, amplitude and frequency are the two important factors. Under external compression load, CFRP composite plate possesses largest amplitude at the loading position during vibration and the smallest amplitude at the boundary. With increasing external compression load, the value of maximum amplitude of CFRP plate increases, which ranges from 1.2 to 3.0 times of the thickness of CFRP plate according to the dataset from extensive literature review (Bouazza & Zenkour, 2020; C.-S. Chen et al., 2002; Fallah & Delzendeh, 2018; Harras et al., 2002; Vinayak Kallannavar et al., 2020; Khalili et al., 2005; Mao et al., 2021; Tang & Dai, 2021; Tang et al., 2020; Z.-X. Wang & Shen, 2011; Zhang et al., 2015). Under such amplitude, the nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP plate ranges from 1.0 to 4.8, which corresponds to the reported frequency ratio of CFRP plate ranging from 1.2 to 3.0 (Shen, 2015). For the modes of vibration considered in this work, when CFRP plate is subjected to external compression load, it undergoes deformation at loading position, and afterwards, the CFRP plate begins to vibrate around the initial position, with the deformation as maximum amplitude and the nonlinear frequency as the period. The developed prediction model is able to predict nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite under a wide range of load levels, sizes, and boundary conditions, which could be used to efficiently evaluate the nonlinear behavior and damage risk of CFRP composite in service, and provide a reference for optimizing the size design of CFRP composite used in constructions. Furthermore, the developed prediction model is able to be used in real-time monitoring system of constructions. The values of external compression loads obtained from sensors are inputted into the developed model to predict the real-time nonlinear frequency ratio of the CFRP composite application. By monitoring the nonlinear frequency ratio, the structure health of real composite structure is assessed and reasonableness of composite structure being designed is evaluated. In the future, coupled effects of these conditions and fiber volume, distribution or environment could be investigated using the developed model based on an extended dataset, which could provide a more comprehensive understanding of vibration behaviors of CFRP composite plate during service life.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, nonlinear vibrations of CFRP composite plate have been investigated using machine learning approach. A prediction model has been developed for calculating the nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite plate with different load levels, length-to-width ratios, width-to-thickness ratios, and boundary conditions. The developed model possesses the evaluated R^2 , RMSE, MAE, MAPE value of 0.96, 0.08, 0.06, 0.05 respectively, which indicate a high accuracy on nonlinear vibration prediction. It is found that with increasing load level, nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite continuously increases due to increasing dynamic stiffness. Meanwhile, under each load level, with increasing length-to-width ratio and width-to-thickness ratio, nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite increases as static stiffness decreases and mass increases. Furthermore, with increasing of boundary constraint, nonlinear frequency ratio of CFRP composite decreases. The findings of this work provide a fundamental understanding of nonlinear vibrations of CFRP composite plate, which contribute to the

prediction of durability of CFRP composite under different conditions. Meanwhile, the machine learning approach could be adopted to study vibration behaviors of composite under effect of environmental conditions, such as moisture or hygrothermal environment.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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